

**ATTRACTING TO THE LEGACY OF LAWFUL AND MANDATORY
HEIRS TO THE LAW OF UZBEKISTAN AND FOREIGN STATES**

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Although the right of succession has preserved its historical nature and function, it has undergone significant changes in the subjects, objects and methods of its implementation. Moreover, at the present time, including with the advent of digital technologies, there are almost all the conditions for the right of inheritance not to be regarded as a property right, but as an institution that defines the legal destiny of property rights and obligations in the citizen's education. Moreover, the universality of the right of inheritance in contemporary circumstances does not exclude the possibility that the heir may leave the place of the heir in individual rights, which requires a different approach to inheritance issues. In this regard, the European Court of Justice is a clear advocate of the need to understand all forms of inheritance, including property, rights and obligations, as inheritance in the resolution of cross-border inheritance issues.

The question of whether or not to define the circle of inheritors and their entitlement to inheritance is of primary importance in the law of the various states among the other elements of inheritance relations, because without defining it, these legal relations cannot be exercised by the subject.

If there is no will, if the testator is denied the right to make a will, if it is found to be invalid, if a portion of the will is inherited against the will, if there are persons who are obliged to inherit, and if the heir has departed from the will, then there is a legal inheritance.

In such a case, the law that establishes the circle of persons entitled to receive

the inheritance covers the absence of the testator's will. In accordance with the law, heirs include, in the first place, the closest relatives of the heir, who can inherit the property in accordance with the will of the testator. However, the order in which heirs and heirs are called to inherit according to the law is not the same in different countries.¹

The legal status of all classes of heirs is irrelevant. Unlike a will, only citizens can legally inherit property, while legal entities such as corporations and others cannot.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, in many European countries, as well as in the CIS countries, the call to legal inheritance is carried out in the order of succession. If there are no heirs in the previous round, each the next round of heirs inherit. However, unlike the law of Uzbekistan, the Functional Codes of Kazakhstan and Ukraine have established a separate rule, i.e. the rules on the sequence of calling the heirs to the inheritance and the amount of their inheritance in the inheritance can be determined by the notarized agreement (contract) of the beneficiary heirs, which arose after the inheritance was cleared. In this way , the law gives the right to the legally entitled heirs to change the procedure of succession established by the law at their own request and by mutual agreement.²

In accordance with the Code of Civil Procedure of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the nominees of the heirs are counted as five. Many authors emphasized that the property of the executor should remain in the family instead of passing to the state, strengthening the lawmaker. But there's a certain amount of thought that goes into it. For example , A.M. Baizigitova calls for the legal heirs to be classified as third-degree relatives, because she considers the excessive "mechanical" expansion of the circle of legal heirs to be incompatible with legal

¹ Barshchevsky M.Y. Inheritance law: Textbook. – M.: Belye Alva, 1996. – 192 p.

² Gushchin V.V., Dmitriev Yu.A. Inheritance law and process: Textbook for higher educational institutions. – M.: Eksmo Publishing House, 2004. - 672 p.

realities, as well as not taking into account the characteristics of family relationships.³

As stated above, the legal heirs agree to the inheritance on an ad hoc basis. Each successive heir is entitled to an inheritance only if there are no predecessor heirs. In this case, the inheritance of the first-in-line heirs in the *tenge* is considered to be a privilege, except for those who inherit by proxy. The inheritance of an estate is dependent on the general income of the legal heirs. According to Article 1135 of the Penal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the children of the executor, spouse and parents are the first-in-line heirs. His children are heirs by right of donation.

If there are no first-degree heirs, then by law the second-degree heirs are the relatives of the deceased, his grandparents from birth. The children of the deceased's brothers and sisters, born and unborn, inherit by the right of representation. Brothers and sisters who are called to inherit may be full siblings (their father and mother are the same) and may not be full siblings (their mother and father may be the same, but the father may be different, and the brothers and sisters may be the same). Siblings and half-siblings (children of persons who are in a second marriage to each other from the first marriage) are not related and do not count in the second line of succession. If there are no heirs in the first and second line, the relatives of the heir (grandparents, aunts and uncles of the heir) are considered to be the third line heirs.

If there are no heirs in the first, second and third line, the third, fourth and fifth degree relatives of the heir are entitled to receive the legal inheritance. The degree of relative is defined by the doctrines that distinguish the relative from one another. The date of birth of the heir is not taken into account. By law, the fifth

³ Kichigin L.F. International legal aspects of German inheritance law and the practice of its application in cases of Soviet citizens. The author's abstract. diss. for the academic degree of the Candidate of Sciences. Law.sciences. – M., 1972. – 22 p.

novelty is included in the circle of heirs, which is the general rule of inheritance by legal kinship, i.e. the heirs are called the heirs' only sons, only daughters, only father and only mother.

In France, the Roman law traditionally classified heirs in accordance with the law and established grades of kinship groups based on the degree of affinity of the brothers to the heir, as a basis for determining their entitlement to the inheritance. The first degree includes the children (children, nephews, etc.) of the heir. In the second degree, the parents of the heir, as well as his brothers and sisters and his paternal relatives are formed. Other descendants of the hereditary chieftain in the third order include the great-grandfather, grandfather, grandmother, In the last group, the fourth group, there are other siblings up to the sixth degree (except for brothers and sisters), and so on. If there are no brothers in the first degree, all the brothers in the second degree are excluded from the inheritance. The procedure involved depriving a close relative of his inheritance. However, as a final rule, the rights of an heir who predeceases the testator are exercised only if the right of succession, which may pass to the testator's descendants, is considered to be the nominative right. For example, the nephews of the testator inherit the estate of the testator's father (i.e., the testator's son) if the testator does not die before the testator's death.

If the testator has no children, the tenge may be distributed when the estate is transferred from the parents. This is the case if one of the parents of the deceased is still alive after the death of the heir, and the child reaches the age of puberty (for example, the son of the mother and father), as well as if the heir has siblings in the third and third degree of puberty (for example, half-siblings and half-siblings).

All brothers of the same rank receive their inheritance in tenge volumes. And if he has parents and brothers and sisters, then one-fourth for each of his parents. The remaining portion is divided among the sisters, brothers and sisters.

A deceased er-khotyn, although not officially included in any of the successions, takes precedence over the heirs of the fourth succession, excluding them from the inheritance and making the property a full property. If there are only two heirs, the surviving spouse will have the right to half of the estate. In other cases , he receives a usufruct for a part of the property (one-fourth in the case of first-degree heirs , half in all other cases)⁴. Usufructu means the right to own property, the right to benefit from the proceeds, the obligation to protect it, but not to bring it to any significant alteration. In this case, the heirs can demand the conversion of the fruits of the vine into a lease for life. In France and Switzerland, the inheritance of kin is regulated by the parentel system. This sequence is based on the ancestral tree, from the hereditary to the past and beyond. His children, his grandchildren, they're born to be pasty and hookah. Parents, children, and grandchildren are added to the list. The first parent consists of the heir and his children, the second parent consists of the parents and their children, and the third parent consists of the grandparents and grandchildren and their children, depending on the age of the heir⁵. This arrangement gives advantage to the first born, and advantage to the youngest. In the first paranthella, the property is divided among the children of the executor in the form of tenge. The remaining children, as in France, inherited by right of nobility. In the second parenthetical case, the property is divided between the parents of the heir: if one of them is not alive, his estate passes to the heirs by proxy, if not, to the surviving parents. The same principles apply in the third and tenth parentels: the outgoing

⁴ Mikhailova A.S. The emergence and development of the institute of inheritance in Russian civil law. The author's abstract. diss. on. Candidate of Sciences, PhD. Jurid. sciences'. – Krasnodar, 2003. – 24 p.

⁵ Inheritance law: Textbook for university students studying in the specialty 030501 "Jurisprudence" / Edited by N.A. Volkova, A.N. Kuzbagarova, O.Y. Ilyina. – 5th ed., reprint. and additional – M.: UNITY-DANA, Law and Law, 2009. – 255 p.

descendants are estranged from the ancestors by the parent line; the property is divided by the parent line in tenge; if there are no relatives in one line, all property is divided in the other line; the descendants inherit by proxy.

German law does not restrict parentage, and the eldest sibling can also be an heir.

In Switzerland, inheritance is limited to the first three parentheses before the law. The siblings (grandparents, grandchildren and great-grandchildren) of the third parent are the sole beneficiaries of the estate of the deceased. In this case, the ownership of property is transferred to the state.

Inheritance laws in the United States are very similar to those in England. That's why most states have a preferential lifetime inheritance policy. For example, in New York State, a married couple is entitled to \$2,000 and one-third of the inheritance if they have two or more children. If you have a child, give him half of what you have, and if you have a wife, give her half of what you have. If there are no relatives of the deceased and the deceased's parents are eligible to inherit, the deceased will give \$25,000 and a portion of the remaining estate to the surviving spouse. If the testator has no heirs in the first line (parents, children and grandchildren), then all heirs will inherit only the living spouse .

When there are no heirs according to the law, or when the heir leaves the estate, the property passes to the state. According to the law of Germany, Switzerland, and Uzbekistan, the state is the legal heir, and as a result, it has not only rights, but also obligations. In France, England, and the United States, the estate of an heirless heir is considered to be no property and is transferred to the state without any compensation.

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